

DETERMINING THE MAXIMUM LENGTH OF A FEEDER USING CRITERIA FOR PERMISSIBLE VOLTAGE DROP AND ACTIVE POWER LOSSES

Chyzhevskiy V.

*Candidate of Technical Sciences,
National Technical University of Ukraine
"Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute",
Kyiv, Ukraine*

ABSTRACT

The selection of the cross-section of a wire or cable conductor during design calculations of feeder parameters for connecting a new consumer or a new source of electrical energy to an existing electrical network requires a number of operational constraints and technical and economic indicators to be taken into account. However, in many cases, this selection is made solely on the basis of the permissible current rating of the wire or cable conductor under steady-state operating conditions, as this approach makes it possible to minimise the calculations at the design stage. Whilst this simplification of the procedure for selecting the cross-section of a feeder wire or cable core is entirely acceptable in many cases, when a high-power consumer or source of electrical energy is connected to the feeder, this approach may lead to excessively high voltage drops and active power losses in the feeder.

This article examines an approach to selecting wire or cable conductor cross-sections based on tables that consider both the limitations on the feeder’s permissible current and the limitations on the permissible voltage drop and permissible active power loss during the transmission of electrical energy along the feeder for various combinations of active load and power factor.

Keywords: feeder maximum length, voltage drop, active power losses.

Introduction

Electrical networks tend to expand continuously, which is caused by the commissioning of new power infrastructure facilities – power lines, transformer substations, and so on. This process is particularly intense in low-voltage electrical networks (up to 1 kV), which form the final stage in the conversion of electrical energy by voltage class and supply power to most consumers.

Connecting a new consumer or source of electrical energy with a high contracted or installed capacity to low-voltage electrical networks usually requires the construction of a new overhead or underground power transmission line to connect that consumer or source to the existing electrical network.

During the design phase of a power transmission line project its key design features are determined, in particular the cross-section of the conductor or cable core used. Proper selection of the conductor or cable core cross-section is a crucial task, as it affects:

- the acceptability of the power transmission line’s operating parameters – in terms of the permissible current in the conductor or cable core;
- the admissibility of the operating parameters of the consumer’s equipment – in terms of the permissible voltage at the end of the power transmission line;

- the economic operating indicators of the power transmission line.

Often, at the project design stage, the exact length of the feeder is not known for certain, as various route options may be under consideration – including the use of both overhead and underground power lines. Such uncertainty significantly complicates designers' tasks, as under these conditions it is not possible to verify whether the wire or cable of the designed feeder complies with the permissible voltage drop or permissible active power loss.

This problem can be effectively solved by referring to tables which can be used to determine the maximum permissible feeder length for various values of wire cross-section and cable core cross-section, active load and power factor, as well as for various permissible values of the voltage drop coefficient and active power losses in the feeder.

The problem of determining the maximum length of a feeder based on the permissible voltage drop

It is known that the Ohm’s law for the low-voltage 3-phase feeder shown in Fig. 1 in conditions of symmetric load can be written as [1]:

Figure 1 – Feeder of electrical network

$$U_0 = \underline{U}_1 + \underline{I} \cdot (R + jX) = (U_1' + jU_1'') + \left(\frac{P - jQ}{U_1' - jU_1''} \right) \cdot (r_0 + jx_0) \cdot L, \tag{1}$$

where:

U_0 – voltage at the beginning of the feeder (real number);
 \underline{U}_1 – voltage at the end of the feeder (complex number);

U'_1, U''_1 – active and reactive voltage components at the end of the feeder;

P, Q – consumer's active and reactive power;

I – feeder line current (complex number);

R, X – feeder resistance and reactance;

r_0, x_0 – feeder per length resistance and reactance;

L – length of the feeder.

After expansion (1) and grouping of the obtained expression in terms of r_0 and x_0 it can be rewritten in the real numbers as:

$$U_0 = U'_1 + \frac{(P \cdot U'_1 + Q \cdot U''_1) \cdot r_0 - (P \cdot U''_1 - Q \cdot U'_1) \cdot x_0}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} + j \frac{(P \cdot U''_1 - Q \cdot U'_1) \cdot r_0 + (P \cdot U'_1 + Q \cdot U''_1) \cdot x_0}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} \cdot L. \quad (2)$$

Given that the maximum permissible value of the feeder voltage drop ΔU_{\max} , %, is known, a system of equations can be derived from (2) to determine the maximum length of the feeder L_{\max} based on the permissible voltage drop:

$$\begin{cases} U_0 = U'_1 + \frac{(P \cdot U'_1 + Q \cdot U''_1) \cdot r_0 - (P \cdot U''_1 - Q \cdot U'_1) \cdot x_0}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} \cdot L_{\max} \\ 0 = U''_1 + \frac{(P \cdot U''_1 - Q \cdot U'_1) \cdot r_0 + (P \cdot U'_1 + Q \cdot U''_1) \cdot x_0}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} \cdot L_{\max} \\ U_1'^2 + U_1''^2 = ((1 - \Delta U_{\max}) \cdot U_0)^2 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The system of equations (3) is consistent, as it contains 3 unknowns – U'_1, U''_1 and L_{\max} .

The maximum permissible value of the feeder voltage drop ΔU_{\max} can be different for different electrical networks. For example, in Ukraine:

- for the 0,4 kV power transmission lines the maximum voltage drop is up to 6 %, excluding voltage drops in internal wiring [2];

- for the lighting systems that are powered directly from the general low-voltage electricity supply system permissible feeder voltage drop is 3% [3];

- for the other low-voltage installations that are powered directly from the general low-voltage electricity supply system permissible feeder voltage drop is 5% [3].

As the feeder's operating conditions must be within the current-carrying capacity of the wire or cable conductor, once the system solutions (3) have been obtained, the following condition must be verified:

$$\frac{P^2 + Q^2}{3 \cdot (U_1'^2 + U_1''^2)} < I_{\max}^2, \quad (4)$$

where:

I_{\max} – maximum permissible current of the wire or cable conductor.

Additional verification must be carried out to check the validity of the calculated values for the real component of the voltage at the end of the feeder U'_1 and the maximum length of the feeder L_{\max} :

$$\begin{cases} U'_1 > 0 \\ L_{\max} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Failure to satisfy conditions (4) and (5) will mean that it is impossible to transmit power $P+jQ$ to the end of the feeder with a specific resistance r_0+jx_0 at a voltage at the beginning of the feeder that equals to U_0 in conditions of providing feeder voltage drop less or equal to ΔU_{\max} . A similar conclusion must be drawn if the system of equations (3) has no real roots or no roots at all.

The problem of determining the maximum length of a feeder based on the permissible active power losses

Given that the maximum permissible value of the active power losses across the feeder ΔP_{\max} , %, is known, a system of equations can be derived from (2) to determine the maximum length of the feeder L_{\max} based on the permissible active power losses:

$$\begin{cases} U_0 = U'_1 + \frac{(P \cdot U'_1 + Q \cdot U''_1) \cdot r_0 - (P \cdot U''_1 - Q \cdot U'_1) \cdot x_0}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} \cdot L_{\max} \\ 0 = U''_1 + \frac{(P \cdot U''_1 - Q \cdot U'_1) \cdot r_0 + (P \cdot U'_1 + Q \cdot U''_1) \cdot x_0}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} \cdot L_{\max} \\ \frac{P^2 + Q^2}{U_1'^2 + U_1''^2} \cdot r_0 \cdot L_{\max} = \Delta P_{\max} \cdot P \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The system of equations (6) is consistent, as it contains three unknowns – U'_1, U''_1 and L_{\max} .

As a rule, the maximum permissible value for the feeder active power losses is not specified in national regulatory documents, as the condition of low-voltage electricity networks and their load levels vary significantly between different distribution system operators operating within the same country. Instead, distribution system operators may set this limit themselves in their own regulatory documents.

The values obtained by solving system (6) must be checked to ensure they satisfy conditions (4) and (5). Failure to satisfy conditions (4) and (5) will mean that it is impossible to transmit power $P+jQ$ to the end of the feeder with a specific resistance r_0+jx_0 at a voltage at the beginning of the feeder that equals to U_0 in conditions of providing feeder active power losses less or equal to ΔP_{\max} . A similar conclusion must be drawn if the system of equations (6) has no real roots or no roots at all.

Practical application of the research results

The results of applying systems of equations (3) and (6) to determine the maximum lengths of low-voltage feeders based on permissible voltage drop and permissible active power losses are illustrated using the example of a NAYY-type cable with aluminium conductors rated at 0,66 kV.

The specific resistance and specific reactance parameters for this cable, as well as the maximum permissible current for the cable conductor when laid underground, for phase conductor cross-sections ranging from 6 mm² to 240 mm², are given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Specifications for NAYY-type 0,66 kV cable

Parameter	Cross-section of a cable's phase conductor, mm ²											
	6	10	16	25	35	50	70	95	120	150	185	240
Specific resistance, Ohm/km	5,110	3,080	1,910	1,200	0,868	0,641	0,443	0,32	0,253	0,206	0,164	0,125
Specific reactance, Ohm/km	0,087	0,082	0,075	0,062	0,061	0,060	0,059	0,057	0,057	0,056	0,056	0,055
Permissible current, A	37	50	67	88	109	136	167	204	236	273	313	369

Table 2 shows the results of the calculation of the maximum feeder length, based on the permissible voltage drop and permissible active power loss, carried out using NAYY-type 0,66 kV cable, for the following conditions:

- source voltage – 400 V;
- load power factor – 0,95;
- permissible feeder voltage drop – 5%;
- permissible feeder active power losses – 3%.

Table 2.

Maximum feeder length, m, based on permissible feeder voltage drop of 5% and permissible feeder active power losses of 3% for NAYY-type 0,66 kV cable

P, kW	Criterion	Cross-section of a cable's phase conductor, mm ²											
		6	10	16	25	35	50	70	95	120	150	185	240
5	ΔU_{max}	295	488	784	1243	1709	2298	3284	4485	5592	6773	8333	10621
	ΔP_{max}	161	267	430	684	945	1279	1850	2559	3234	3968	4979	6521
10	ΔU_{max}	148	244	392	622	854	1149	1642	2243	2796	3386	4167	5311
	ΔP_{max}	80	133	215	342	473	640	925	1279	1617	1984	2489	3260
20	ΔU_{max}	74	122	196	311	427	574	821	1121	1398	1693	2083	2655
	ΔP_{max}	40	67	107	171	236	320	462	640	808	992	1245	1630
30	ΔU_{max}	–	81	131	207	285	383	547	748	932	1129	1389	1770
	ΔP_{max}	–	44	72	114	158	213	308	426	539	661	830	1087
40	ΔU_{max}	–	–	98	155	214	287	411	561	699	847	1042	1328
	ΔP_{max}	–	–	54	85	118	160	231	320	404	496	622	815
50	ΔU_{max}	–	–	–	124	171	230	328	449	559	677	833	1062
	ΔP_{max}	–	–	–	68	95	128	185	256	323	397	498	652
75	ΔU_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	153	219	299	373	452	556	708
	ΔP_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	85	123	171	216	265	332	435
100	ΔU_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	–	164	224	280	339	417	531
	ΔP_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	–	92	156	162	198	249	326
150	ΔU_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	226	278	354
	ΔP_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	132	166	217
200	ΔU_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	265
	ΔP_{max}	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	163

In Table 2 the symbol “–” indicates combinations of the cross-section of the feeder cable conductor or wire and the active load of the consumer connected at the end of the feeder for which conditions (4) or (5) were not met.

An analysis of Table 2 shows that, for a cable power transmission line, the criterion for determining the maximum feeder length based on permissible active power losses is more stringent than the criterion based on permissible voltage drop.

To facilitate the process of selecting the cross-section of a wire or cable conductor during the feeder design stage, tables may be drawn up for different types of wires and cables, different values of load power factors, and so on.

Conclusions

This paper proposes an approach to determining the maximum length of a low-voltage feeder based on permissible voltage drop and permissible active power losses, which is based on the use of tables compiled for various combinations of wire and cable types, active load power, load power factor, and so on.

The advantage of this approach is that it significantly simplifies the procedure for selecting the cross-

section of a wire or cable conductor, particularly at the initial stages of design calculations, when the initial information required to carry out the calculations is incomplete.

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